

Examples of \mathcal{KC} -maps and \mathcal{KD} -maps on topological ordered spaces

Wanbok Lee^a, Hoonjoo Kim^b

^aDepartment of Mathematical Sciences, Seoul National University, Seoul 08826, Korea

^bDepartment of mathematics education, Sehan University, Jeollanam-do, 58447, Korea

Abstract

We give examples of multimap classes \mathcal{KC} and \mathcal{KD} in topological ordered spaces. We obtain generalizations of results of Jeng, Huang, and Zhang [10] and introduce an abstract setting on the KKM theory on ordered spaces as in Park [14].

Keywords: Abstract convex space, KKM theorem, KKM space, mapping classes \mathcal{KC} , \mathcal{KD} , \mathcal{B} , connected ordered space

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1. Introduction

In early 1990's, Park introduced the admissible class \mathcal{A}_c^k of multimaps in the KKM theory. Since then there have appeared new classes of multimaps such as the KKM class, the S-KKM class, the 'better' admissible class \mathcal{B} , and their modifications. Those classes of multimaps were first applied to convex spaces and later to generalized convex spaces (simply, G-convex spaces).

From 2006, Park [11] introduced a new concept of abstract convex spaces and multimap classes \mathcal{K} , \mathcal{KC} , and \mathcal{KD} having certain KKM property which are adequate to establish the KKM theory. With this new concept, Park [12] generalized and simplified known results of the theory on convex spaces, H-spaces, G-convex spaces, and others. Moreover, in his previous work [13], Park gave examples of multimap classes \mathcal{KC} , \mathcal{KD} , and \mathcal{B} in abstract convex spaces, and generalizations of results of Jeng, Huang, and Zhang [10] which contains some interesting examples of \mathcal{KC} -maps.

In the present paper, our aim is to give examples of multimap classes \mathcal{KC} , \mathcal{KD} , and \mathcal{B} in topological ordered spaces. The study of such spaces was initiated by Horvath and Llinares Ciscar [4] and followed by Luo [8, 9].

Section 2 is concerned with definitions of abstract convex spaces and multimap classes \mathfrak{KC} and \mathfrak{KD} . As in [13], we also give comments and observations on results of Jeng, Huang, and Zhang [10], where some interesting examples of \mathfrak{KC} -maps on abstract convex spaces or connected ordered spaces were given.

In Section 3, we introduce the topological semilattice with path-connected intervals which are typical examples of connected ordered spaces. We also note that an order theoretic version of the KKM principle in [4] can be regarded as a special case of the KKM theorem on abstract convex spaces.

Finally, Section 4 deals with generalizations of the results in Section 2 and, consequently, we have plenty of new examples of \mathfrak{KC} -maps and \mathfrak{KD} -maps.

2. Abstract convex spaces and multimap classes \mathfrak{KC} and \mathfrak{KD}

This section is concerned with definitions of abstract convex spaces and multimap classes \mathfrak{KC} and \mathfrak{KD} .

Let $\langle D \rangle$ denote the set of all nonempty finite subsets of a set D .

Definition 2.1. An *abstract convex space* $(E, D; \Gamma)$ consists of a nonempty set E , a nonempty set D , and a multimap $\Gamma : \langle D \rangle \multimap E$ with nonempty values. We may denote $\Gamma_A := \Gamma(A)$ for $A \in \langle D \rangle$.

When $D \subset E$, the space is denoted by $(E \supset D; \Gamma)$. In such case, a subset X of E is said to be Γ -convex if, for any $A \in \langle X \cap D \rangle$, we have $\Gamma_A \subset X$. In case $E = D$, let $(E; \Gamma) := (E, E; \Gamma)$.

An abstract convex space with any topology is called an *abstract convex topological space*.

Typical examples of abstract convex spaces are convex subsets of topological vector spaces, convex spaces due to Lassonde, c -spaces (or H -spaces) due to Horvath, and generalized convex (simply, G -convex) spaces due to Park; see [11] to [13] and references therein.

Definition 2.2. Let $(E, D; \Gamma)$ be an abstract convex space and Z a set. For a multimap $F : E \multimap Z$ with nonempty values, if a multimap $G : D \multimap Z$ satisfies

$$F(\Gamma_A) \subset G(A) := \bigcup_{y \in A} G(y) \quad \text{for all } A \in \langle D \rangle,$$

then G is called a *KKM map* with respect to F . A *KKM map* $G : D \multimap E$ is a KKM map with respect to the identity map 1_E .

A multimap $F : E \multimap Z$ is called a \mathfrak{K} -map if, for any KKM map $G : D \multimap Z$ with respect to F , the family $\{G(y)\}_{y \in D}$ has the finite intersection property. We denote

$$\mathfrak{K}(E, Z) := \{F : E \multimap Z \mid F \text{ is a } \mathfrak{K}\text{-map}\}.$$

Similarly, when Z is a topological space, a \mathfrak{KC} -map is defined for closed-valued maps G , and a \mathfrak{KD} -map for open-valued maps G . Then, we have

$$\mathfrak{K}(E, Z) \subset \mathfrak{KC}(E, Z) \cap \mathfrak{KD}(E, Z).$$

Note that if Z is discrete then three classes \mathfrak{K} , \mathfrak{KC} , and \mathfrak{KD} are identical.

For an abstract convex topological space $(E, D; \Gamma)$, the *KKM principle* is the statement $1_E \in \mathfrak{KC}(E, E) \cap \mathfrak{KD}(E, E)$. A *KKM space* is an abstract convex space satisfying the KKM principle. If we have only $1_E \in \mathfrak{KC}(E, E)$, then we call E as a *partial KKM space*.

We know relations between multimap classes \mathfrak{KC} and \mathfrak{KD} as in the following theorem. For a proof, we need to remind the following facts about normal spaces; see Bourbaki [1] and Lefschetz [7].

A topological space X is normal iff point-finite open cover $\mathcal{U} = \{U_\alpha \mid \alpha \in I\}$ of X is *shrinkable*, that is, an open cover $\mathcal{V} = \{V_\alpha \mid \alpha \in I\}$ exists such that $\bar{V}_\alpha \subset U_\alpha$ for each $\alpha \in I$.

For a normal space X and a finite family $\{A_1, \dots, A_n\}$ of closed subsets of X , there exists a *thickening family* of open sets of X such that $A_i \subset U_i$ for all $1 \leq i \leq n$, and for every sub-family $\{A_{i_1}, \dots, A_{i_k}\}$, we have $A_{i_1} \cap \dots \cap A_{i_k} \neq \emptyset$ iff $U_{i_1} \cap \dots \cap U_{i_k} \neq \emptyset$.

Theorem 2.3. *Let $(X, D; \Gamma)$ be an abstract convex space, Z a topological space, and $F : X \multimap Z$. Suppose that for any $A \in \langle D \rangle$, the set $F(\Gamma_A)$ in its induced topology is a normal space. If $F \in \mathfrak{KC}(X, Z)$, then $F \in \mathfrak{KD}(X, Z)$.*

Proof. Let $F \in \mathfrak{KC}(X, Z)$ and $G : D \multimap Z$ be an open-valued KKM map with respect to F . For $A \in \langle D \rangle$ and $B \subset A$, we have $F(\Gamma_B) \subset G(B)$, so $\{F(\Gamma_B) \cap G(y)\}_{y \in B}$ is an open cover of the normal space $F(\Gamma_B)$. By shrinkability, there exists an open cover $\{V_{B_y}\}_{y \in B}$ of $F(\Gamma_B)$ such that $\overline{V_{B_y}} \subset G(y)$ for all $y \in B$. Here, we can think $\overline{V_{B_y}}$ as a closed subset of Z . Define a map $H : D \multimap Z$ by

$$H(y) := \begin{cases} \bigcup_{y \in B \subset A} \overline{V_{B_y}} & \text{for } y \in A \\ Z & \text{for } y \in D \setminus A. \end{cases}$$

Then $H(y) \subset G(y)$ for all $y \in A$ and H is closed-valued since the number of subsets of A is finite. For any $B \subset A$, $F(\Gamma_B) \subset \bigcup_{y \in B} V_{B_y} \subset H(B)$. So H is a KKM map with respect to $F \in \mathfrak{KC}(X, Z)$, that is, $\{H(y)\}_{y \in D}$ has the finite intersection property. Hence $\bigcap_{y \in A} G(y) \supset \bigcap_{y \in A} H(y) \neq \emptyset$. Therefore, $\{G(y)\}_{y \in D}$ has the finite intersection property.

Remark 2.4. Note that in Kulpa and Szymanski's example of a partial KKM space which is not a KKM space, they used a non-normal subspace $[0, 1/2) \cup (1/2, 1]$ of $[0, 1]$; see [6].

The following corollary is Proposition 2.7 in [6]:

Corollary 2.5. *Let $(X; \Gamma)$ be an abstract convex space that satisfies the partial KKM principle. If X is a normal space and Γ is a closed-valued map, then $(X; \Gamma)$ is a KKM space.*

Theorem 2.6. *Let $(X, D; \Gamma)$ be an abstract convex space and Z a normal space. Then $\mathfrak{KD}(X, Z) \subset \mathfrak{KC}(X, Z)$.*

Proof. We follow the proof of Theorem 4.2 in [13]. Let $F \in \mathfrak{KD}(X, Z)$ and $G : D \multimap Z$ be an closed-valued KKM map with respect to F . For $A \in \langle D \rangle$, we have $F(\Gamma_A) \subset G(A)$. By thickening, we can make a family $\{U_y\}_{y \in A}$ of open subsets of Z such that $G(y) \subset U_y$ for all $y \in A$ and for every $J \subset A$, we have $\bigcap_{z \in J} U_z \neq \emptyset$ iff $\bigcap_{z \in J} G(z) \neq \emptyset$. Define a map $H : D \multimap Z$ by

$$H(y) := \begin{cases} U_y & \text{for } y \in A \\ Z & \text{for } y \in D \setminus A. \end{cases}$$

For $J \in \langle D \rangle$, $H(J) = Z$ if $J \cap A \neq \emptyset$. If $J \subset A$, then $H(J) = \bigcup_{z \in J} U_z$ and $F(\Gamma_J) \subset G(J) \subset \bigcup_{z \in J} U_z$. In short, $G(y) \subset H(y)$ for $y \in D$. Therefore H is an open KKM map with respect to $F \in \mathfrak{KD}(X, Z)$ and $\{H(y)\}_{y \in D}$ has the finite intersection property. Hence $\bigcap_{y \in A} U_y \neq \emptyset$ which is equivalent to $\bigcap_{y \in A} G(y) \neq \emptyset$. Thus, $\{G(y)\}_{y \in D}$ has the finite intersection property.

From Theorem 2.3 and Theorem 2.6, we obtain the following corollary:

Corollary 2.7. *Let $(X, D; \Gamma)$ be an abstract convex space, Z a normal space, and $F : X \multimap Z$. If the set $F(\Gamma_A)$ in its induced topology is a normal space for any $A \in \langle D \rangle$, then $\mathfrak{KC}(X, Z) = \mathfrak{KD}(X, Z)$.*

Proof. If Z is a normal space, then $\mathfrak{KD}(X, Z) \subset \mathfrak{KC}(X, Z)$ by Theorem 2.6. If the set $F(\Gamma_A)$ in its induced topology is a normal space for any $A \in \langle D \rangle$, then $\mathfrak{KC}(X, Z) \subset \mathfrak{KD}(X, Z)$ by Theorem 2.3.

In 2002, Jeng, Huang, and Zhang [10] obtained some interesting examples of \mathfrak{KC} -maps on convex spaces or nonempty intervals on the real line. In [13], Park gave some comments and observations on results of [10]. In Section 4 in the present paper, we show that some of the results in [10] and some of the comments to them in [13] can be generalized. Consequently, we give new examples of \mathfrak{KC} -maps and \mathfrak{KD} -maps on abstract convex spaces or connected ordered spaces.

Now, we are concerned with results for abstract convex spaces.

Theorem 2.8. *Let $(X; \Gamma)$ be an abstract convex space, $(Y; \Omega)$ an abstract convex topological space, and $F : X \multimap Y$ such that, for each $A \in \langle X \rangle$, $F(\Gamma_A)$ is Ω -convex in Y .*

- (1) *If $1_Y \in \mathfrak{KC}(Y, Y)$, then $F \in \mathfrak{KC}(X, Y)$.*
- (2) *If $1_Y \in \mathfrak{KD}(Y, Y)$, then $F \in \mathfrak{KD}(X, Y)$.*

Proof. (1) Suppose $G : X \multimap Y$ is a closed-valued KKM map with respect to F . For $A \in \langle X \rangle$ and $x \in A$, choose $y \in F(\Gamma_{\{x\}})$ and define a function $\sigma : A \rightarrow Y$ by $\sigma(x) = y$. Put $N = \sigma(A)$. Define $H : Y \multimap Y$ by

$$H(y) := \begin{cases} \bigcap_{x \in \sigma^{-1}(y)} G(x) & \text{for } y \in N \\ Y & \text{for } y \in Y \setminus N. \end{cases}$$

For $M = \{y_1, y_2, \dots, y_m\} \subset N$ and $y_i \in M$, choose a $x_{j(i)} \in \sigma^{-1}(y_i)$ and let

$$A_j = \{x_{j(1)}, x_{j(2)}, \dots, x_{j(m)}\},$$

then $\sigma|_{A_j} : A_j \rightarrow M$ is an 1-1 correspondence. Since $M \subset F(\Gamma_{A_j})$ and $F(\Gamma_{A_j})$ is Ω -convex, $\Omega_M \subset F(\Gamma_{A_j})$. Therefore

$$\Omega_M \subset \bigcap_{j=1}^{\Sigma|\sigma^{-1}(y_i)|} F(\Gamma_{A_j}) \subset \bigcap_{j=1}^{\Sigma|\sigma^{-1}(y_i)|} \bigcup_{i=1}^m G(x_{j(i)}) \subset \bigcup_{i=1}^m \bigcap_{x \in \sigma^{-1}(y_i)} G(x) = H(M).$$

Hence H is a KKM map with respect to 1_Y . So $\emptyset \neq \bigcap_{y \in N} H(y) \subset \bigcap_{x \in A} G(x)$.

(2) can be proved in the same way as (1).

Since a G-convex space is a KKM space and a convex space is a G-convex space, we have the following corollaries.

Corollary 2.9. *Let $(X; \Gamma)$ be an abstract convex space, $(Y; \Omega)$ a G-convex space, and $F : X \multimap Y$ such that, for each $A \in \langle X \rangle$, $F(\Gamma_A)$ is Ω -convex in Y . Then $F \in \mathfrak{KC}(X, Y) \cap \mathfrak{KD}(X, Y)$.*

Corollary 2.10. *Let X and Y be two convex spaces and $F : X \multimap Y$ satisfy that $F(C)$ is convex for any convex subset C of X . Then $F \in \mathfrak{KC}(X, Y) \cap \mathfrak{KD}(X, Y)$.*

For the case (1) of Theorem 2.8, we may assume that $\overline{F(\Gamma_A)}$ is Ω -convex in Y instead of Ω -convexity of $F(\Gamma_A)$. From this, we have the following Theorem 2.2 of [10] as a corollary.

Corollary 2.11. *Let X and Y be two convex spaces and $F : X \multimap Y$ satisfy that $\overline{F(C)}$ is convex for any convex subset C of X . Then $F \in \mathfrak{KC}(X, Y)$.*

3. Topological semilattices with path-connected intervals

We need the following definition in Horvath and Llinares Ciscar [4]:

Definition 3.1. A *semilattice* (or a *sup-semilattice*) is a partially ordered set $X = (X, \leq)$ such that each $(x, x') \in X \times X$ has a l.u.b. $x \vee x'$. Note that each $A \in \langle X \rangle$ has a l.u.b. denoted by $\sup A$. In (X, \leq) , for each $(x, x') \in X \times X$ with $x \leq x'$, the set $[x, x'] := \{y \in X \mid x \leq y \leq x'\}$ is called an *order interval*.

For a semilattice (X, \leq) and an $A \in \langle X \rangle$, define $\Delta(A) := \bigcup_{a \in A} [a, \sup A]$. A subset C of X is said to be Δ -convex if, for any $A \in \langle C \rangle$, we have $\Delta(A) \subset C$.

A *topological semilattice* (or a *topological sup-semilattice*) is a topological space X with a partial order \leq for which it is a semilattice with a continuous sup operation (i.e. the function $\vee : X \times X \rightarrow X, (x, x') \mapsto x \vee x'$ is continuous).

Note that (X, Δ) becomes an abstract convex spaces and a topological semilattice is an abstract convex topological space. For more wide understanding, see Park [14].

Example 3.2. 1. In [4], six non-trivial examples of topological semilattices are given.
 2. Several examples of connected ordered spaces are topological semilattices.

The following is the order theoretic version of the KKM principle in [4] (Theorems 1 and 1’):

Theorem 3.3. *Let $(X; \Delta)$ be a topological semilattice with path-connected intervals. Then $1_X \in \mathfrak{KC}(X, X) \cap \mathfrak{KD}(X, X)$.*

The following generalizes Theorem 3.3:

Theorem 3.4. *Let $(X; \Gamma)$ be an abstract convex space, $(Y; \Delta)$ a topological semilattice with path-connected intervals, and $F : X \multimap Y$ such that, for each $A \in \langle X \rangle$, $F(\Gamma_A)$ is Δ -convex in Y . Then $F \in \mathfrak{KC}(X, Y) \cap \mathfrak{KD}(X, Y)$.*

Proof. By Theorem 3.3, we have $1_Y \in \mathfrak{KC}(Y, Y) \cap \mathfrak{KD}(Y, Y)$. Then the conclusion follows from Theorem 2.6.

Remark 3.5. Park [14] noted that the above theorems are results of the fact that a topological semilattice with path-connected intervals is a KKM space.

4. \mathfrak{KC} -maps and \mathfrak{KD} -maps on ordered topological spaces

In this section, we show that some of the results in Section 2 can be generalized. First, we can modify the Theorem 2.3 of Jeng, Huang, and Zhang [10] as follows:

Theorem 4.1. *Let $(X; \Delta)$ be a totally ordered and connected topological space, Y a topological space, and $F : X \multimap Y$ such that $F([a, b])$ is connected in Y for each $a, b \in X$ with $a < b$. Then $F \in \mathfrak{KC}(X, Y) \cap \mathfrak{KD}(X, Y)$.*

Proof. Since every finite set can be linearly ordered, we can follow the proof of Theorem 2.3 in [10] with necessary modifications.

Remark 4.2. In Theorem 4.1, if we assume that $\overline{F([a, b])}$ is connected in Y instead of $F([a, b])$, then $F \in \mathfrak{KC}(X, Y)$.

When X is an interval of \mathbb{R} , then the above remark reduces to the following Theorem 2.3 of [10].

(I) *Let X be a nonempty interval of \mathbb{R} and Y a topological space. If $F : X \multimap Y$ satisfies that $\overline{F([a, b])}$ is connected for any $a, b \in X$ with $a < b$, then $F \in \mathfrak{KC}(X, Y)$.*

Similarly, we have

(I)’ *Let X be a nonempty interval of \mathbb{R} and Y a topological space. If $F : X \multimap Y$ satisfies that $F([a, b])$ is connected for any $a, b \in X$ with $a < b$, then $F \in \mathfrak{KC}(X, Y) \cap \mathfrak{KD}(X, Y)$.*

Example 4.3. Let $X = Y = [0, 1]$ with the usual topology, and let $F : X \multimap Y$ be defined as

$$F(x) := \begin{cases} \{|\sin 1/x|\}, & \text{for } x \in (0, 1]; \\ \{0\}, & \text{for } x = 0. \end{cases}$$

This example was originally given to show that $\mathfrak{KC}(X, Y) \not\supseteq \mathfrak{A}_c^c$. Now it is also an example of (I) and (I)’. See [2].

Note that the converses of (I) and (I)’ are not true:

Example 4.4. Let $F : [0, 1] \rightarrow [0, 1]$ be defined by $F(0) := \{0, 1\}$ and $F(x) := \{1\}$ for $x \in (0, 1]$. Since F has a continuous selection $f(x) = 1$, $F \in \mathfrak{KC}(X, Y) \cap \mathfrak{KD}(X, Y)$, but $\overline{F([0, b])}$ and $F([0, b])$ are not connected for any $b \in (0, 1]$.

The class of maps having connected graph is quite large:

Lemma 4.5. (Hiriart-Urruty [5] Theorem 3.2]) *Let X, Y be a topological spaces, $C \subset X$ a connected subset, and $\Gamma : X \multimap Y$ be a multimap with connected values on C . Either of the next assumptions ensures that the graph of $\Gamma|_C$ is connected:*

- (a) Γ is l.s.c.
- (b) Γ is u.s.c. and compact-valued.

A map $\Gamma : X \multimap Y$ is called a *connectivity map* if the graph over each connected subset of X is a connected set. This concept was introduced by Nash for single-valued case; see Girolo [3].

From Theorem 4.1 and Lemma 4.5, we have the following:

Theorem 4.6. *Let $(X; \Gamma)$ be a connected totally ordered space, Y a topological space, and $F : X \multimap Y$. Then $F \in \mathfrak{KC}(X, Y) \cap \mathfrak{KD}(X, Y)$ if it satisfies one of the following conditions:*

- (i) F is a connectivity map.
- (ii) F is l.s.c. with connected values.
- (iii) F is u.s.c. with compact connected values.
- (iv) F has connected values and open fibers.
- (v) F is a closed compact map with connected values.

Proof. (i) Since F is a connectivity map and $[a, b]$ is connected for each $a < b$ in X , $F|_{[a,b]}$ has connected graph. Therefore, $F([a, b])$ is connected. Hence, by Theorem 4.1, the conclusion follows.

(ii), (iii) By Lemma 4.5, F is a connectivity map. Therefore, (ii) \implies (i) and (iii) \implies (i).

(iv) Since $F^{-1}(y)$ is open for each $y \in Y$, F is l.s.c. Indeed, for each open set $A \subset Y$, we have

$$F^{-1}(A) = \{x \in X : F(x) \cap A \neq \emptyset\} = \bigcup_{y \in A} F^{-1}(y)$$

is open. Therefore, (iv) implies (ii).

(v) It is well-known that a closed compact map is u.s.c. with compact values. Therefore, (v) implies (iii).

Theorem 4.7. *Let $(X; \Gamma)$ be an abstract convex space, Y a topological space, and $F \in \mathfrak{KC}(X, Y) \cup \mathfrak{KD}(X, Y)$ such that $F(x)$ is connected for each $x \in X$. Then $F(\Gamma_A)$ is connected for each $A \in \langle X \rangle$.*

Proof. Suppose that $F(\Gamma_A)$ is not connected for some $A \in \langle X \rangle$. Then there exist two nonempty disjoint closed [resp. open] subsets U and V of Y such that $F(\Gamma_A) \subset U \cup V$. Moreover, there exist two points $p, q \in \Gamma_A$ such that $F(p) \cap U \neq \emptyset$ and $F(q) \cap V \neq \emptyset$. Since $F(p)$ and $F(q)$ are connected, $F(p) \subset U$ and $F(q) \subset V$. Define a map $G : X \multimap Y$ by $G(p) := U$, $G(q) := V$, and $G(x) := Y$ for $x \notin \{p, q\}$. Then G is closed-valued [resp. open-valued] and

$$F(\Gamma_B) \subset G(B), \quad \text{for all } B \in \langle X \rangle.$$

Therefore G is a KKM map with respect to F . But $G(p) \cap G(q) = \emptyset$ contradicts $F \in \mathfrak{KC}(X, Y) \cup \mathfrak{KD}(X, Y)$. This completes our proof.

Remark 4.8. 1. If $F \in \mathfrak{KC}(X, Y)$ such that $\overline{F(x)}$ is connected for each $x \in X$, then $\overline{F(\Gamma_A)}$ is connected for each $A \in \langle X \rangle$.

2. In Theorem 2.4 of [10], the authors claimed that, if X is a convex space, Y a topological space, and $F \in \mathfrak{KC}(X, Y)$ such that $\overline{F(x)}$ is connected for each $x \in X$, then $\overline{F(C)}$ is connected for each convex subset C of X .

3. In [10], an example showing that the converse of the above claim does not hold is given.

[10] gives an example showing that the converse of the above assertion does not hold.

The following theorem characterizes maps in \mathfrak{RC} and \mathfrak{RD} :

Theorem 4.9. *Let $(X; \Gamma)$ be a connected totally ordered space, Y a topological space, and $F : X \multimap Y$ a multimap such that $F(x)$ is connected for each $x \in X$. Then $F \in \mathfrak{RC}(X, Y) \cap \mathfrak{RD}(X, Y)$ if and only if $F([a, b])$ is connected for each $a, b \in X$ with $a < b$.*

Proof. This follows from Theorems 4.1 and 4.7.

Remark 4.10. In Theorem 4.9, if F is such that $\overline{F(x)}$ is connected for each $x \in X$, then $F \in \mathfrak{RC}(X, Y)$ if and only if $\overline{F([a, b])}$ is connected for each $a, b \in X$ with $a < b$.

For single-valued maps, Theorem 4.9 reduces to the following:

Corollary 4.11. *Let $(X; \Gamma)$ be a connected totally ordered space, Y a topological space, and $f : X \rightarrow Y$. Then $f \in \mathfrak{RC}(X, Y) \cap \mathfrak{RD}(X, Y)$ if and only if $f([a, b])$ is connected for each $a, b \in X$ with $a < b$.*

Remark 4.12. In Corollary 4.11, $f \in \mathfrak{RC}(X, Y)$ if and only if $\overline{f([a, b])}$ is connected for each $a, b \in X$ with $a < b$.

When X is an interval of \mathbb{R} , then the above remark reduces to the following Theorem 2.5 of [10]:

(II) *Let X be a nonempty interval of \mathbb{R} , Y a topological space and $f : X \rightarrow Y$. Then $f \in \mathfrak{RC}(X, Y)$ if and only if $\overline{f([a, b])}$ is connected for any $a, b \in X$ with $a < b$.*

As an immediate consequence of (I)' and Theorem 4.9, we have

(II)' *Let X be a nonempty interval of \mathbb{R} , Y a topological space and $f : X \rightarrow Y$. Then $f \in \mathfrak{RC}(X, Y) \cup \mathfrak{RD}(X, Y)$ if and only if $f([a, b])$ is connected for any $a, b \in X$ with $a < b$.*

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